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An Internet of Engineering Lab Things

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ABSTRACT

We have completed the first phase of a large-scale synchronous remote engineering laboratory with large class sets of experiments, and low latency video, and data and control interactions. We based our system around a large class set of 88 National Instruments Educational Laboratory Virtual Instrumentation Suites (NI ELVIS) and 324 top boards. Of the 240 top boards available to the second stage electronics course that will first use the lab, there are six types. Two were available commercially, and four were designed in-house. We report on the curriculum context that drove the design processes behind these boards, with a particular focus on the challenge of giving distance learners of electronics the same learning opportunities as campus-based students. The boards are accessed through a reconfigurable HTML5 interface (one per experiment) that mimics the reconfigurable nature of a typical electronics test bench. Virtually instant responsiveness is provided via peer-to-peer video streams and websocket connections for data and control.

Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Engineering Education, Curriculum Development, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: Electronics, synchronous laboratories, peer-to-peer communications, low-latency control, data, and video

INTRODUCTION

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Preparing engineering students for their careers now means preparing them to operate in a connected world. With commercial activities spanning the globe, it is no longer possible to assume that graduate engineers will be working in the same time zone as their colleagues or their equipment, let alone in the same building. Other vital applications of remote equipment in the professional engineering world include cases where the environment is too hazardous for humans, perhaps due to extreme pressure, temperature, radiation, contaminants, moving machinery or inaccessibility. Together our two organisations (educator and equipment supplier) are well placed to allow students to explore the remote usage of equipment during their engineering degree, because all students are distance learners. The question we have posed ourselves, is how can distance learners of electronics experience the same learning opportunities as campus based-students? Particular aspects of interest to us are the ease of access to the equipment, the ability to configure your working area to suit your preferences, and the speed of the interaction.

1 CONTEXT

1.1 State of the art

The remote presentation of practical work can take a number of forms. Simulation-based and hardware-based approaches both have their merits. For example, simulation environments are highly scalable, and are becoming ever more realistic with the introduction of virtual reality techniques [1]. Hardware based approaches have the benefit of including difficult-to-compute stochastic and non-linear effects without risk of introducing misleading artefacts due to the limitations of simulations. With the growing prevalence of computing devices in laboratory environments, the involvement of computers in mediating the learning process would seem inevitable [2].

Students typically either access a hardware-based remote experiment directly, and interact with it in real time (synchronously), or set parameters for a batch job to run when the equipment can schedule the experiment (asynchronously). Asynchronous experiments can service many students by running well-controlled experiments in an efficient manner. Synchronous experiments tend to be less resource efficient because they permit extended, continuous student exploration, but they offer value in that a variety of conditions can be explored in a safe manner, some erroneously, providing self-led experiential learning [3]. Synchronous interactions with remote laboratories allow tutor support [4]. Synchronous remote laboratories are also dependent on the communications infrastructure. It is well known that even small delays can cause the human brain to expend effort in memorisation [5], so latency is undesirable. The continuing world-wide effort to provide routine broadband connectivity provides an opportunity for synchronous remote laboratory experiences to reach a wider geographic audience without suffering from noticeable delay. This has been a major interest for us.

Data gathering in remote laboratories appears to produce better learning outcomes when performed individually [6]. This indicates the value in selecting equipment for remote experiments that is inexpensive enough that large class sets can be commissioned. Aside from the resource scheduling benefits, this also helps address one of the barriers to institutional laboratory sharing [7]. Large class sets of equipment can address the immediate needs of organisations that have large classes (numbering several hundreds or more) that wish to add practical work provision with a short lead time.

1.2 Local curriculum

Building on [the academic institution's] existing expertise in remote laboratories, we will allow students to have remote hands-on learning experience without having to invest in individual hardware for each student. We have implemented large class sets

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1. Reconfigurable interface mimics the reconfigurable nature of an electronics test bench (a) schematic of a test bench, (b,c) screenshots of the web interface for an electronics activity relating to alternating current (at present stage of development).

of experiments, based around a set of 88 National Instruments ELVIS II+ boards, with connectivity to the PC running experiments in LabVIEW via a USB interface.

The NI ELVIS includes 12 instruments such as an oscilloscope (100 MS/s), digital multimeter (5.5 digits), function generator (10 V_{pp}), variable power supply (+15 V), Bode analyzer, and other common lab instruments in a compact form factor allowing for a space efficient set-up. All instruments and IOs are available and accessible through software and are connected to the devices to test and control physically through a connector. The connector is open allowing connectivity to off-the shelf top-boards or custom designed boards.

We have built rack space and internet connections sufficient to support over two hundred simultaneous experiments, each connected to a single student or a small group. This equates to nearly 5000 hour-long sessions available per day.

Our first major curriculum usage is for a second stage electronics course, and we are provisioning the lab with 40 sets of each experiment, including a mixture of the off-the-shelf top boards from Quanser (pendulum, mechatronic actuators), and custom designed boards (sensing, ranging, digital electronics). This enables us to use the same set-up based on the NI ELVIS platform.

1.3 Infrastructure

We have built a communications infrastructure around peer-to-peer video and websockets, to enable virtually instantaneous responsivity no matter where on earth the students may be, relative to the equipment, so long as broadband connectivity is available. We have successfully accessed experiments in trials from the UK, Europe, the USA, Hong Kong, China and New Zealand, whilst retaining perceived lag-free operation.

2 INTERFACE

2.1 HTML5

Students connect to the equipment via an HTML5 interface, which gives them authentic access to genuine real-time data, and enables a wide range of computing and mobile devices to be used. A live video, live data streams, controls, and analysis routines are available in each interface. The interfaces are customised for each experiment. An example of a screen is shown in Fig. 1(b,c). We have moveable and resizable windows within the webpage that mimic the way that typical bench equipment can be moved and reconfigured as the practical work proceeds.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Approach

Our first use of this particular remote laboratory is in a new stage two electronics course that is one quarter of a year's study contribution to an accredited general engineering degree. The course highlights the role of sensors, logic and actuators in enabling electronics systems to interact with the real world, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. The sensing, logic and actuation cycle that we focus on in our second stage electronics course

Since the degree course does not have a pure electronics engineering focus, we are using a driven pendulum as a mechanical source of signals that are analogous to alternating current waveforms, thus bridging more mechanically-minded students into the abstract world of invisible electronic signals. It also serves as mathematical preparation for future exercises on the Fourier series, by challenging them to

correctly identify the amplitude and frequency of the sine wave they produced from the pendulum (see Fig 1.c).

We selected a second commercially available top-board for the last experiment. For the remaining experiments, we developed our own ELVIS top-boards so that we could take advantage of the remote learning environment most effectively. Photographs of the latest prototypes of our top boards are shown in Fig.3, with the light/strain board in Fig. 3(a), the ranging board in Fig. 3(b), the Fourier exercise in Fig. 3(c), and the digital exercise in Fig. 3(d).

Table 1. ELVIS-based experiments for stage two electronics course

Name	No.	Source	Learning
Pendulum	44	Quanser	Distinguish amplitude and frequency of AC signals
Sensors	40	Own	Explore role of resistors in buffering circuits
Ranging	40	Own	Manipulate raw sensor data to obtain meaning
Fourier	40	Own	Ability to identify patterns in noisy data
Digital	40	Own	Operation of logic gates
Motors	40	Quanser	Strengths and weakness of different motors

The sensors board measures light and strain in two separate experiments. The strain experiment has a structural beam subjected to bending by a servo, with two strain gauges. One is driven by a constant current source, the other is in a Wheatstone bridge that has an amplifier circuit on the output. Students can then directly compare the results obtained by each approach and assess them against criteria such as circuit complexity and signal quality. The light experiment contains three pairs of light emitting diodes and photodiodes (two visible, one infrared) and a rotating drum with a surface that is progressively shaded from white to black. One of the visible photodiodes is connected to a commercially-available current-to-voltage amplifier. The other two photodiodes (one visible, one infrared) are connected to current-to-voltage amplifiers with programmable feedback resistors. This allows the students to see the effect of adjusting the resistor value across a wide range, and to gauge the sensitivity of the circuit.

The ranging board has ultrasonic and infrared ranging sensors, and a calibration target that moves linearly. One sensor reports a distance measurement directly, while the other gives a voltage measurement that is non-linearly related to the distance. The students must unravel the calibration challenge, and then can scan a rotating area that contains three objects (cylinder, square section tube and triangular section tube). We have included a triangular object so that at certain angles of the rotating table, it will disappear from the ranging trace by deflecting the probe signals, and if it is shadowing another object, that 'disappears' as well. In this way, students will be able to appreciate challenges encountered by real world sensing systems such as those in autonomous cars.

The Fourier board allows the students to control the generation of a rectangular wave of 12.5%, 25% or 50% duty cycle, so that the Fourier decomposition exercise is conducted on a signal that they have generated themselves. The different duty cycles produce different harmonic patterns, and there are additional peaks arising

from imperfections in the system. The interface has an exercise that encourages students to exercise judgement over whether a peak in the frequency domain is part of the expected signal, or from the noise.

Fig. 3 Custom top-boards for ELVIS designed in house for remote laboratories in a second stage electronics course (a) light and strain sensors, (b) ultrasonic and infrared ranging sensors (rest of board with automated targets not shown), (c) rectangular-wave generator for Fourier exercise, (d) close-up of part of the digital electronics board.

The digital board is intended to expose to view the inner workings of circuits comprised of logic gates, allowing logic values to be probed directly, anywhere in the circuit. It is also intended to replicate the challenge of a conventional laboratory where abstract logic circuits must be converted into concrete wiring diagrams before they can be physically realised. Neither of these goals is particularly well met by programmable logic systems, such as field programmable gate arrays (FPGA), programmable logic controllers (PLC) and microcontrollers. For these systems, the inner connections cannot be directly probed, and often the wiring diagrams (or their equivalent) are calculated automatically for the user.

Instead, we have put a dozen 74LS series CMOS chips onto a board along with light emitting diodes on every input and output. We provide a schematic editor in the HTML5 interface that represents those chips, in the positions that occupy on the board, and let the student connect the pins by drawing wires. The student is free to wire the chips in any way they wish. The wiring is accomplished in the digital board by using a clocked virtual wiring network. The wiring network comprises a serial-to-parallel register to write to all the input pins, and a parallel-to-serial register to read all the output pins after they have settled. A wire drawn by the student is implemented

as a table lookup in the output values. This approach can handle all the possible circuits that the student can wire up. For example, the board readily handles the feedback loops and race conditions found in an edge-triggered set-reset flip-flop implemented with two pairs of cross-coupled NAND gates (nine NAND gates in total).

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We have completed the first phase of a large-scale synchronous remote engineering laboratory. We had begun the task by asking how can distance learners of electronics experience the same learning opportunities as campus based-students? For ease of access to the equipment, and supporting the preference of distance learners to individually gather remote data, we implemented large class sets of experiments. So far we have 88 NI ELVIS base units and 324 top boards, including custom and off-the-shelf designs. This offers an overall value proposition that is attractive compared to asynchronous and virtual environments.

The NI ELVIS units combine multiple test instruments into a single unit. Together with our HTML5 interfaces, which have movable and resizable windows, we mimic the reconfigurable nature of a conventional electronics test bench. We also made the interaction virtually instantaneous by using peer-to-peer video and websocket connections for data and control. Via an appropriate broadband connection, these are virtually lag-free from almost anywhere in the world.

Thus we can say that with the appropriate choice of communications infrastructure, and experimental equipment, the pedagogic needs of remote engineering education can be met using synchronous remote laboratories. Together our two organisations have demonstrated our alignment on the future of engineering education, whether remote or face-to-face, so as to prepare students to thrive in a connected world.

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